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**CAIRT mission product test data set descriptions for
case/impact studies UTLS O3 OSSE**

README-4

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<p><i>Abstract</i></p> <p>This document describes the simulated CAIRT L2 profiles of ozone, water vapour and carbon monoxide used as test dataset-product (TDS-P) in the CAIRT Phase A Performance and Requirement Consolidation study.</p>		
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List of acronyms

ACT	ACross Track
ALT	ALong Track
AK	Averaging Kernel
BASCOE	Belgian Assimilation System for Chemical Observations
CAIRT	Changing Atmosphere Infra-Red Tomography explorer
CAMS	Copernicus Atmosphere Monitoring Service
ECMWF	European Centre for Medium range Weather Forecast
EnKF	Ensemble Kalman Filter
MIAP	Mission Impact Assessment Plan
MLS	Microwave Limb Sounder
MLT	Mesosphere Lower Thermosphere
MO	Mission Objective of CAIRT
OSSE	Observing System Simulation Experiment
PerReC	CAIRT Performance and Requirement Consolidation study
SciReC	CAIRT Scientific and Requirement Consolidation study
SO	Scientific Objective of CAIRT
STE	Stratosphere-Troposphere Exchange
TDS-P	Test Data Set-Product
UTLS	Upper Troposphere Lower Stratosphere
WP	Work Package (of PerReC if no other project mentioned)

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1 Introduction

The purpose of this document is to provide a description of the test data set product (TDS-P) produced for the CAIRT impact study on UTLS OSSE during the CAIRT Performance and Requirement Consolidation study. Here, TDS-P are simulated CAIRT L2 profiles produced following this chain of processes:

1. Select a model Nature Run (NR) providing reference atmosphere for O₃ and H₂O
2. Regridding NR onto the CAIRT retrieval grid, leading to NR@CAIRT
3. Simulate CAIRT L2 profiles given NR@CAIRT, the Fast Level 2 Simulator (FL2S version 0.9.3dev0) and the Linear Performance Estimation (LPE version 3) of CAIRT
4. The simulated CAIRT profiles are to be assimilated by the BASCOE-EnKF assimilation system. In its implementation, in each model time step, BASCOE-EnKF needs to invert a matrix whose size depends on the number of observations. The size of this matrix exceed the available memory of the BIRA-IASB HPC when model is running with a time step of 30 minutes as usually used in BASCOE. (CAIRT has around 12 times more observations than MLS which is regularly assimilated by BASCOE.) During Phase 0, the time step was reduced to 7,5 minutes. In Phase A, superobservations have been used where observations inside a common model grid cell for a common time step are aggregated.

These steps are defined in Sect. 2. In order to compare the added values of CAIRT against the current reference limb instrument MLS, MLS observations have also been simulated, which are described in Sect. 3. The file format of CAIRT superobservation and MLS are described in Sect. 4. The codes and configuration files used to produce this TDS-P are stored on the BIRA-IASB subversion system as detailed in the different subsections of this document and in Sect. 5. References are given in Sect. 6.

2 Simulating CAIRT L2 profiles

2.1 The Nature Run (NR)

The nature run we are looking for is supposed to have a good representation of ozone (O₃) in the UTLS, as well as water vapour (H₂O). Here we will use the CAMS control run HLQD (cycle 47r3) in operation between September 2021 and March 2022 (Schoenhardt et al., 2023). This model simulation is done with a horizontal Gaussian grid N256 (i.e. around 40 km horizontal resolution), with 137 vertical levels with a vertical resolution around 300 m in the UTLS and decreasing toward the surface and has 3-hourly outputs (instead of 6-hourly for the CAMS operational analysis). CAMS HLQD is based on a model including a detailed representation of the tropospheric chemistry and a linear representation of the stratospheric ozone. For water vapour, we have used the specific humidity from HLQD. Note that its representation of is biased, where it is too wet in the lower stratosphere and is missing the oxidation of methane in the stratosphere. Moreover, HLQD does not include the injection of water vapour from the Hungu eruption. Cloud fractions, necessary to flag out CAIRT data in presence of clouds are also taken from HLQD.

HLQD is stored in the ECMWF MARS archiving system and Table 1 provides the MARS parameters to retrieve it, and has been downloaded at BIRA-IASB. The command used to retrieve and download this dataset is:

```
> my_retrieve.sh hlqd_FC_N256.cfg
```

which uses the script `get_slurm.ksh_20230303`. These scripts and config file are stored in the BIRA-IASB subversion repository (see Sect. 5).

Table 1: Information to access the CAMS HLQD experiment on the ECMWF MARS system for a given date where YYYY-MM-DD is between 2021-08-01 and 2022-03-31

class	rd
expver	hlqd
stream	oper
type	fc
step	3/to/24/by/3
levelist	1/to/137
levtype	ml
params	Insp/t/q/go3/co/cc*
date	YYYY-MM-DD
grid	N256

* Where: Insp=log of surface pressure, t=temperature, q=specific humidity used for water vapour, go3=ozone, co=carbonyl monoxide and cc=cloud fractions.

2.2 Regridding the nature run onto the CAIRT retrieval grid (NR@CAIRT)

The regridding of NR onto the CAIRT L2 retrieval grid is done using a subset of the BASCOE system, namely BASCOE-MAO (Model At Observation). BASCOE being a data assimilation system, it includes libraries to read model fields and observation files, and an observation operator to interpolate the model fields at the geolocation of the observations. In its MAO configuration, model fields are taken from snapshot files instead of being simulated by the BASCOE model. (This is the procedure used to validate stratospheric ozone from CAMS analysis and forecast in the CAMS Evaluation and Quality Control – EQC – project, namely CAMS2_82, see, e.g. Schoenhardt et al., 2023)

Here, the model fields are the HLQD three hourly snapshot files. The CAIRT L2 retrieval grid for the period September 2021 – March 2022 is produced using the CAIRT retrieval grid simulator (sim_CAIRT_grid.py developed during Phase 0 and available at https://jugit.fz-juelich.de/cairt-scirec/sim_CAIRT_grid). This code uses as input the CAIRT orbit simulated in Phase 0 for one year and stored on Zenodo (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10262729>). Here, the CAIRT retrieval grid assumes a swath of 500 km with 25 km ACT resolution. Simulating CAIRT L2 profiles with 100 km ACT resolution is done in FL2S (see the ATBD of the Scientific Work Bench, Höpfner et al., 2025).

The procedure is then the following. For each day:

1. produce CAIRT retrieval grid file with time and location of the retrieved profiles using the sim_CAIRT_grib.py.
2. run the script mao.sh which call BASCOE-MAO, where species and cloud fraction from HLQD 3-hourly snapshots of one day are interpolated (in space and time) onto the CAIRT retrieval grid. These files are called HLQD@CAIRT (or NR@CAIRT).

All the versions of these scripts and codes are given in Sect. 5 which are calling each day as follows:

```
> ./sim_CAIRT_grid.py -ORB -o dirname_of_CAIRTL2_grid -l 0 -t 40 -L o3,cc,h2o,co YYYYMMDD
> ./mao.sh -w workdir -E HLQD -d YYYYMMDD -M path2NR -O filename_of_CAIRTL2_grid -o
dirname_of_HLQD@CAIRT
```

2.3 Perturbing NR@CAIRT using LPE and FL2S

The daily files of NR interpolated onto the CAIRT retrieval grid (i.e. NR@CAIRT) are perturbed and smoothed according to CAIRT errors from Linear Performance Estimation (LPE v3), done using FL2S (v 0.9.3dev0 and described in the SWB ATBD, Höpfner et al., 2025).

Given NR@CAIRT daily file and LPE files, FL2S simulates CAIRT simulated L2 profiles of O₃ and H₂O. A quality flag is created to account for cloud contamination in FL2S, and the scenario file cloud_impact_cth5-22_0.003.dat, described in (Höpfner et al., 2025).

For this TDS-P, the FL2S codes are using the configuration file config_CAIRT-PhA-IS40.py. This config file defines, in particular, the setup for producing initial seed for uncorrelated random number generation. The initial seed value is saved in each daily TDS-P to ensure reproducibility. The FL2S codes, the config file and the cloud scenario cloud_impact_cth5-22_0.003.dat are stored on the FZJ git repository or the BIRA-IASB subversion system (see Sect.5). The config file is also given in Sect. 5. For each day, the following call is made:

```
> ./fl2s_run.py -OA -f NR@CAIRT_file -o CAIRT_L2_filename config_CAIRT-PhA-IS40.py
```

Note that CAIRT L2 files are created in the NOB file format described in the SWB ATBD.

2.4 Super observations

Due to the CAIRT spatial resolution, the number of CAIRT profiles are much larger than past limb instrument like MLS. These are large datasets that can lead to problem in data assimilation. For example, EnKF system like BASCOE has a memory fault error when trying to assimilated CAIRT simulated L2 profiles because the size of a matrix that the EnKF has to invert is too large. This is a well-known problem in data assimilation where the solution is to build superobservations. In this setup, observations inside the same model grid cell for the same model time step are aggregated as described in (Höpfner et al., 2025) using the code mk_superobs.py. It takes on input the filename with the CAIRT L2 data as well as the filename where to store CAIRT L2 “superprofiles”. This code is stored on the FZJ github (see Sect. 5) and is called for each day as follows:

```
> ./mk_superobs.py -Ovr file_with_model_resolution -o CAIRT_L2super_filename -m 1 CAIRT_L2_filename.
```

3 Simulating MLS observations

The computation of MLS simulated profiles differs from the computation of CAIRT profiles where here we can take advantage that some of the necessary data already exist. This is the case for the retrieval grid of MLS, the a priori profile, the error profile and vertical averaging kernels of MLS. The MLS retrieval grid (i.e. vertical pressure grid, time, latitude and longitude of the profiles), a priori and L2 error profiles are taken from MLS v5 daily observation files that can be downloaded here: <https://mls.jpl.nasa.gov/eos-aura-mls/data.php>. MLS v5 vertical averaging kernels are given for five latitudes, independent of time and longitude, are can be downloaded from the same place.

CAMS HLQD are interpolated onto the MLS retrieval grid using BASCOE-MAO as for CAIRT (see Sect. 2.2), and are the perturbed as follows:

$$y = Ay_m + (I - A)y_a + y_p$$

where y_m is HLQD interpolated onto the MLS grid; y_a are the existing MLS a priori profile corresponding to the MLS geolocation; A is the MLS vertical averaging kernel matrix and I is the identity matrix. The perturbation profile y_p is the Gaussian random profile multiplied by the MLS error profile available in MLS data files. This means that MLS simulated data does not take into account MLS systematic error.

Profiles are only assimilated in the vertical range of validity given in Livesey et al. (2020, denoted L2020 hereafter). L2020 also states were to accept/discard profiles using the variable “estimated precision”, “quality”, “convergence” and “status” given in MLS files. These values from real MLS L2 profile files have been used to flag out some profiles or the lower part of them. This screening discards profiles contaminated by clouds, with only few profiles of O₃ and CO being affected.

MLS L2 profiles are simulated with the `sim_mls.py` code (see Sect. 5) which call each day as follows:

```
> ./sim_mls.py -vOd YYYYMMDD.
```

4 TDS-P file description for UTLs OSSE

TDS-P files (CAIRT superobservations and MLS) are formatted in netCDF, as described in Table 5 and 6 in of the ATBD about the scientific work bench (Höpfner et al., 2025).

5 Versions, traceability and reproducibility

The codes and configuration files used to produce this TDS-P are either on the BIRA-IASB subversion system or on the FZJ CAIRT git repository. In the first case, all codes are below the following directory: <https://svn-intern.aeronomie.be/ae/COMMON>, in the second case, all codes are in `jugit.fz-juelich.de:cairt-scirec`. Code names, their corresponding processes, their location in the subversion/git system and their revision numbers are given in Table 4.

Table 2: Code names, their corresponding processes, their location in the subversion system and their revision numbers are given in Table 4 for **the version 0.2 of this document**. All codes are available under <https://svn-intern.aeronomie.be/ae/COMMON>.

Code/config name	Process	Code location starting at below https://svn-intern.aeronomie.be/ae/COMMON	revision number
<code>my_retrieve.sh</code> , <code>get_slurm.ksh_20230303</code> , <code>hlqd_N256_FC.cfg</code>	NR download	stand-alone/CAIRT/PhA/IS40/0_NR	13052
<code>sim_CAIRT_grid.py</code>	CAIRT retrieval grid simulation	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14264704	
<code>mao.sh</code>	Regridding NR onto the CAIRT retrieval grid	stand-alone/CAIRT/PhA/IS40/2_mao	13041
BASCOE-MAO exec	Regridding NR onto the CAIRT retrieval grid, called by <code>mao.sh</code>	atmos/bascop/branches/qe10.00.00	13057
<code>fl2s_run.py</code>	simulation of CAIRT L2 profiles	(git) <code>cairt_fl2s/main</code>	r252e3a3e
<code>mk_superobs.py</code>	make CAIRT daily L2 super-obs. given CAIRT daily L2 file	(git) <code>cairt_superobs/main</code>	r532d0000
<code>sim_mls.py</code>	simulate MLS daily L2 file	stand-alone/CAIRT/PhA/IS40/3_simL2	13044

Content of `config_CAIRT-PhA-IS40.py`:

```
para2ref = {
  'h2o': '_mrd_thres_ref_1',
  'o3': '_mrd_thres_ref_2',
  'co': '_mrd_thres_ref_1',
}

lpe_ncdir = "/home/quentin/CAIRT/FL2S/lpe_v3_mrd_thres/ncfiles/"

CSSn = 'IS40'

mod_ncdir = "/bira-iasb/projects/CAIRT/data_t2/PhA/IS40/2_atGRID/hlqd/CAIRT_RG_B1.4/"

# define fl2s parameters
sol_activity = 0 # solar activity index (within 0 for low activity and 1 for high activity). The default is 0.
n_cal = 56 # calibration period length (in terms of acquisitions). The default is 100.
akd_threshold = 0.003 # averaging kernel threshold. The default is 0.003.
ak_noise_sys = {
  'ak':{'noi':False,'sys':False},
  'aknoi':{'noi':True,'sys':False},
  'aksys':{'noi':False,'sys':True},
  'aknoisys':{'noi':True,'sys':True},
}

# define across-track bins for different across-track averaging lengths of the lpe
act_bin_ind = {
  100:[[2,6],[6,10],[10,14],[14,18]],
  300:[[2,14],[2,14],[6,18],[6,18]],
}

# random generator seed method
# - auto: fixed seed based on date and target name + `random_seed` (below)
# - fixed: uses `random_seed` for all targets and dates
# - random (or anything else): no specific seed used, gives non-reproducible results
random_seed_method = "auto"

# fixed random seed or extra "jitter" for "auto"
random_seed = 55903915
#random_seed = np.random.randint(123456789)

# for faster test set to positive number to calculate only nmod_use samples along the tracks;
nmod_use = 100

css_config = {
  'IS40': dict(
  )
}

# Cloud mask information
cld_fraction_lim = 0.2 # Mask will be set for cloud fraction above cld_fraction_lim (if "cc" in model input
scenario file)
#cld_impact_file = "cloud_impact_cth5-16_0.003.dat"
```

```
#cld_impact_file = "cloud_impact_cth5-21_0.003.dat"  
cld_impact_file = "/home/quentin/CAIRT/git_julich/cairt_fl2s/cloud_impact_cth5-22_0.003.dat" # The  
most stringent case
```

```
# Path to temporary directory  
scratch="/home/quentin/CAIRT/svn/PhA/IS40/3_simL2/test"
```

6 Literature

Höpfner, M., Funke, B., Errera, Q., Raspollini, P., Sinnhuber, B.-M., Ungermann, J., 2025. CAIRT linear SWB ATBD (No. DEL-04-01a-ATBD-CAIRT-PhAPerReC-1.1).

Livesey, N.J., Read, W.G., Wagner, P.A., Froidevaux, L., Lambert, A., Manney, G.L., Millán, L.F., Pumphrey, H.C., Santee, M.L., Schwartz, M.J., Wang, S., Fuller, R.A., Jarnot, R.F., Knosp, B.W., Martinez, E., Lay, R.R., 2020. Earth Observing System (EOS) Aura Microwave Limb Sounder (MLS) Version 4.2x Level 2 and 3 data quality and description document (No. D-33509 Rev. E). JPL.

Schoenhardt, A., Arola, A., Benedictow, A., Bennouna, Y., Bouarar, I., Cuevas, E., Errera, Q., Eskes, H.J., Griesfeller, J., Ilic, L., Kapsomenakis, J., Langerock, L., Mortier, A., Pison, I., Pitkänen, M.R.A., Ramonet, M., Richter, A., Schulz, M., Tarniewicz, J., Thouret, V., Tsikerdekis, A., Warneke, T., A. A. Zerefos, 2023. Validation report of the CAMS near-real-time global atmospheric composition service, Period September - November 2022 (No. doi:10.24380/rrmj-aj0k).